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Design and Development of an Integrated e-Lesson Plan: A Composite Tool in the Online Teaching of Dance

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Abstract: *A shift from F2F to online teaching in open and distance learning mode necessitated a simple and easily accessible teaching tool for conducting online teaching of a traditional dance programme involving practical skills. It led to the design and development of an integrated e-lesson plan, a model which could be used in any LMS as a resource interface and a primary component of instructional design. The e-lesson plan, basically an e-document, was used in the g-suite learning space where a programme of 6 months duration in dance was conducted for students enrolled from across the country. The paper shows the process of development and application of the lesson plan as a synergetic space, with components from different courses taught on a single platform. This multimodal lesson plan with audio, video and text is set in a step-by-step instructional framework to provide the learner with the situatedness of a classroom. The integrated nature of the tool emphasized the culture of learning important for a subject like dance and explored to offer the students the experience of a community of practice. The effectiveness of this programme that was offered using this technology was evaluated using a survey. The results of the survey showed that the students reacted positively to the shift to online mode, the use of new pedagogical tools, its accessibility, the content framework of the weekly e-lesson plan, and other components of the instructional design.*

Keywords: *Instructional design, e-lesson plan, dance education, online teaching of dance, e-learning of Bharatanatyam, open and distance learning, ICT, communities of practice, situated learning.*

Introduction

Digital technology has been used in creating dance works in dance since the 1960s as could be seen in the works of choreographers like Noll in 1967 and

Cunningham in 1968. The last decade of the 20th century saw expansion in the development of software like Life Forms, Motion Builder, Maya and other 3D human figure animations and other augmented tools that facilitated choreographers to collaborate with artists across time and distance. Likewise, several word processing type editors, customized with Labanotation or Benesh notation, were developed to be used in composing, editing and sharing dance scores (Calvert et al, 2005). However, it has been only in the past two decades with expansion in e-networking that this medium began to be used for teaching dance through the web. Studies on the effectiveness of technology in dance education have changed the paradigms of traditional teaching methods. More so when it concerns distance learning, acquiring motor skills that are primary in kinesthetic learning of dance has been using technologies of teleconferencing, multimedia like CD-ROMs and F2F teaching.

Bonbright (1999) noted that it had become imperative for art instructors to be both artists and educators as it was as educators that artists understood the content, process, the methodology of developing and delivering curricula, syllabi and assessments. Today, it is equally pertinent for art instructors to be adept at using available digital multimedia components that can translate their instructional design onto the web. The use of technology-assisted learning has had to imbibe ICTs in a form it has never been used before. The task is to translate the pedagogy involved to an online built-in environment with both static and dynamic inputs in a seamless way. The learning management systems like Moodle, Blackboard, Canvas or Google classroom or those in MOOCS like SWAYAM (Study Webs of Active-Learning for Young Aspiring Minds), supported by the Indian government, and other web learning services that provide Web 2.0 environments, can efficiently act as platforms to deliver the courses.

Rationale and Objectives of the Study

Distance learning of dance in India is a recent phenomenon starting from the early years of this millennium. A look at the distribution of courses on dance and their delivery mechanism shows that the courses being offered at affiliated colleges and universities² range from Certificate to Bachelor and Master in dance where it is delivered in the form of study materials or books and audio-video CDs along with face2face teaching component offered from off-campus centres called study centres. *Kathak, Bharatanatyam, Manipuri or Kuchipudi* and other classical dance forms form the usual specialized subject areas that were once traditionally passed on mostly from a specific class of performers and gurus in the medieval times till teaching became institution based mainly during the rise of Indian nationalism in the early 1930s. The transfer of knowledge from guru to shishya in traditional dance teaching has had more to do with intense training of the student to become dancers and dance makers. With the inclusion of dance as a subject

in higher education, this was extended to further understand its role in socio-cultural history and its importance in other domains. But notably, the closely knit relation between a guru and shishya still holds steady in the Indian context in training aspects of technical dance skills. This importance was extended in f2f training offered at distance education institutions in the form of contact programmes.

IGNOU too had addressed the problem of distance by adopting a blended learning approach with weekend f2f practical classes at study centres for its courses on dance from the year 2009 (when it was first initiated). Apart from this, it has also relied consistently on technologies of teleconference, electronic media and multimedia through its various services like *Gyan Darshan*, *Gyan Vani*, and *e-Gyankosh* for imparting courses of both theory and practical nature. The online revolution in education-based course delivery during the first decade of this century, followed by the acceptance of MOOCs as a way of democratizing knowledge transmission brought in a new demand for diversification. This coupled with stress on online as an economically viable option to reach out to students spread sporadically over the country with a lesser number in clusters of programme study centres, the counselling and training for the course on dance was shifted to be offered directly from a single window from head-quarters at New Delhi. Consequently, a change in the mode of course delivery from distance with f2f to online mode was emphasized from 2018 onwards and the delivery modality of the dance courses thus entailed an overhaul. The transition to online delivery of courses had to weigh its importance mainly against overcoming the limitations of proximity between the teacher and learner which was till now available in f2f classes in dance training. Kinesthetic learning in dance that primarily dealt with acquiring motor skills and was directly taught by teachers had to be now converted into an effective framework consisting of e-learning instructional modules. The challenge was to efficiently fulfill the teacher's objectives and address the student's needs for undertaking fundamental-level courses in dance skills in online mode.

The prime aim of the present research was to create a structure of a composite tool in the form of an online interface like an e-lesson plan that could play an active part in interactive instructional design which may be readily offered on any LMS. The study intended to implement such a model for the students enrolled in Jan 2020 and also test it by inviting feedback which could be evaluated for making further changes in the offered model. It was felt that developing integrated learning systems with e-lesson plans as a prime part of the instructional design could lead towards creating a composite platform for teaching traditional dances to fresh learners that would also be a step to overcome the hesitancy to explore online teaching of traditional dance skills.

The main objectives of this research were to:

1. Create a structure for an online interface model in the form of integrated weekly lesson plans that would:

- a) provide learning and execution support for students to ensure step-by-step learning experience in basic skills in a traditional dance;
 - b) set up targets that can be measured against objectives with continuous formative assessments for the learning undertaken;
 - c) create points to reflect upon the tasks done and the upcoming ones yet to be undertaken; and
 - d) ensure emotional support and awareness of aspects of health and injury prevention to cope with a physically demanding routine.
2. Conduct and evaluate feedback for the *integratede-lesson plan* model adopted for teaching students the fundamental skills of Bharatanatyam.

Literature Review of Online Dance Education Methods Involving Dance Practical Teaching

Before the concept and use of LMS for online learning majorly with the creation of the first open-source LMS-Moodle in 2002, virtual 3D animation tools were extensively used by the late 90s to create a web learning environment. Nevertheless, networking through emails and messages was used for feedback and discussion as in the case of the concept of tele-learning that was accomplished through Virtual-U, an e-learning tool of Simon Fraser University. It was used along with Life forms, a 3D software in their online course on dance for campus and distance collaborative learning, and dance creation (Garland & Naugle, 1997). In the WebDANCE project that was conducted online teaching of traditional Greek dance and English dances, e-learning lessons with audio, video, texts and digitized dances using 3D motion capture were made available on a special WebDANCE website. The instructional design was structured as chapters and sub-chapters with each sub-chapter having a series of self-paced lessons. As the project covered different traditional dances, every dance was marked as a chapter and the many aspects of the dance like presentation, activity, event and tradition were delineated as the sub-chapters (Kavakli, et al., 2004, 2007). It was similar to the course-block-units order followed in IGNOU self-learning materials. Each lesson had learning goals, activities, resources and evaluation tasks.

Theory-based or blended courses have been effectively using web-based models and studies have shown how the use of web-based technologies has catered to different educational demands in dance curricula. A blended course in professional issues in ballet that was implemented for classical ballet education for secondary students was hosted by the Croatian academic and research network (CARNet) using localization of the Moodle learning system. This course consisted of heavy multimedia components consisting of short audio and videos that addressed the study about challenges faced by professional ballet dancers. Courses are divided into weeks each with two or three lessons with materials for learning in the form

of audio-video and text. Every week consists of an introductory lesson with a review of contents and activities and a conclusive summation before completion along with a test or discussion. Making the course accessible online was a step aimed at adapting the ballet curriculum to technological changes and improving the quality of ballet education (Racic, Jandric, & Vucina, 2011). Without replacing f2f teaching, the blended mode in courses also sometimes restricts itself to only offer online resources on Moodle in the form of blogs, videos, e-portfolio, PowerPoint lectures, quizzes and learner support as in chat and the discussion forum for teaching undergraduate dance (Dias et al., 2018). Many dance-making and choreography tools use dance interactive learning systems to explore, create and combine new movements using motion capture, and virtual and augmented reality. As they exist as stand-alone tools for collaborative work without being inbuilt into an LMS, studies on them do not come under the purview of this paper. The role of technology has also been explored to be integrated to give the learners of dance possible training in its application in areas like sound design, video production and editing, creation of e-portfolio, press or media-related design and so on (Risner & Anderson, 2008) and also as an effective means of providing feedback on online written assignments (Risner, 2014).

Methods

The methods of study have involved both primary and secondary data analysis. Literature pertaining to previous work in the area of online education in dance coupled with a review of pedagogical areas relevant to learning approaches, instructional designs, and online adaptations of these in the LMS in dance teaching-learning were some of the secondary materials used for contextual analysis. The study design to explore the online framework to be offered for the programme of dance skills used theoretical formulations that allowed student-centric interactions possible in an online mode with specific concerns on the area of kinesthetic, psychomotor and cognitive areas in course development. An integrated e-lesson plan was developed and implemented for the students admitted in the January 2020 session.

Following this, a survey was conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of the programme on its web-based mode of delivery on Google classroom during the mid-session. Data was collected through google forms from all sixteen (16) students of the January 2020 batch certificate programme and five (5) previously registered students who had opted to complete their courses in that session. The survey sought opinions on different matters regarding the online mode of class delivery and was conducted in the Google classroom. The questionnaire consisted of items dealing with: the skill and responsiveness of the instructor, perceptions on course content, accessibility, workload, assessment, interactivity, flexibility, the effectiveness of lesson plan structure and some open-ended subjective questions

on their preferences and views on probable areas of course improvement. The data received were analyzed using simple frequency and percentages. The responses were automatically summarised by the online software and for those with open-ended short answers, data were documented to incorporate changes in the plan outline in successive sessions.

Pedagogical Context and Approach

Providing personalized instruction, cooperation, feedback and creative interaction between the medium and the user are important when it comes to online learning. Interactive multimedia inputs in the instructional design make the applications in computer-assisted instruction accessible. With wide-ranging apps, software and learning platforms available for making this a reality, the possibility and scope of online learning in dance have advanced. But, at the same time, the delivery of the instructional material through asynchronous and synchronous means has its challenges because many of such courses on dance on which studies have been undertaken as seen in the literature review above are either built upon the student's previous practical experience or are components of blended learning supported with f2f component. Technologically supported instructional design is an important tool for knowledge construction both for cognitive learning and skill development (Mayer & Moreno, 2003). Huss et al. (2015) stress technology's role in engagements and social interactions to enable self-sustaining and high-quality education in distance education pedagogies. The role of instructional design in the online teaching of traditional dance has been primarily to facilitate and guide the students in advancing from simpler to complex skills in the presence of supportive elements to reach the goal. Effective learning strategies have become predominant markers of teaching-learning of dance skills or dancing techniques in the digital era as the learners are as Parrish noted, "motivated to customize and take charge of their own learning" (2016).

The teaching-learning of basics in traditional dance involves a behaviourist learning framework in its instructional design as it is targeted at reaching the intended goals of performing the skills taught. The resources and data that are imparted tend to always fulfill the objectives presented at the beginning with the outcomes-based assessment undertaken at the end. The cognitivist approach is found to be useful in organizing and presentation of resources in an effective manner with elements of information recall, interactivity and diverseness. Design principles from the cognitive theory of multimedia learning are effective guidelines for creating such learning environments (Mayer, 1997). As the teaching of basic dance skills largely pertains to the psychomotor domain of learning involving muscle memory, the expected levels of response in behaviour would range from guided responses to complex overt responses involving various stages of imitation, manipulation, precision, articulation and naturalization (Dave, 1967; Simpson, 1972).

The stages of adaptation and origination that leads to change, modification or creation of the new matter as in Simpson's model, which can be equated with the non-discursive communication of Harrow, would be an important part of the final stages of learning the basics (Simpson, 1972; Harrow, 1972).

Learning dance skills involves a lot of practice and the student gets trained in different aspects of presenting the dance form. However, it is essential that the learning be situated in the context of composing, performing and presenting which would make the student better equipped and competent enough to satisfy the objective of undergoing the course. Composing for productions or experiential learning through internships with production troupes are some means of doing that. 'Situated learning' by Lave and Wenger proposed that "learning involved a process of engagement in a community of practice" (Smith, 2003). As Wenger states "Communities of practice are groups of people who share a concern or a passion for something they do and learn how to do it better as they interact regularly" (2015). The learners share a common purpose, ideas and challenges with the support provided as they prepare to train themselves as dance makers or performers in their shared community of practice of learning the skill. From learning step-by-step in an inductive manner following a behaviourist approach, the student can be led to face a situation-specific problem thus contextualizing their learning following a constructivist paradigm. Here they practice to develop, share and maintain their specific knowledge for a professional identity. A situated learning experience can be provided during the course of training the students wherein different components of dance making and performance which are usually discussed separately in different courses have the probability of being applied holistically and tested in a classroom situation or outside it with or without the mentorship of a teacher. Situated learning theory suggests that to learn effectively, students need to perceive their discipline as a culture and participate in that culture as apprentices (Lave & Wenger, 1991). As Brown, et. al (1989) state, "Cognitive apprenticeship methods try to enculturate students into authentic practices through activity and social interaction in a way similar to that evident- and evidently successful-in craft apprenticeship". The performance strategies and skills imparted are tools that would exist isolated unless the students are shown how to use them and see through a performer's or a composer's eyes. It provides the students with the opportunity to enter the culture of dance practice.

Open and distance education model that until now dealt with self-directed learning through SLMs focusing on individual minds to follow a linear sequence of cognitive psychology development has to open up to turn its focus on building social and cultural interaction emphasizing the contextualizing of learning that is stressed by theories of situated cognition. The concept of *arena* according to Lave (1988) is a "physically, economically, politically and socially organized space-in-time" that is a "setting" for the activity that the learner is engaged in. About viewing the

classroom as a learning environment Darwin stated, “the physical space and contents of the classroom become only two aspects of the setting. The ways that learners “personally order and edit” (Lave, 1988, p. 71) classroom arenas become the most powerful aspects of settings” (2006). The f2f learning sessions or synchronous online classes provide the impetus to create this ambience of a setting for a student in open and distance learning. However, this idea of context or setting should to a greater extent be initiated for a classroom in the online instructional design on an LMS platform itself and this is the challenging part. This challenge has been dealt with in the teaching of online dance skills with the help of an integrated e-lesson plan. Bloom’s taxonomy’s six categories of representing cognitive skill levels have catered to writing learning objectives, designing activities and creating outcomes-based assessments in instructional design. And so have ADDIE’s or the SAM model, Dick and Carey and others. Gagne’s nine *instructional events* provide a framework of step-by-step processes involved in presenting the contents of the learning approach which can be directly adapted to strategize an effective instructional plan. It deals with 3 essential stages in the delivery of instruction: the actual presentation of instruction and the steps before it and after it. These events of Gagne’s correspond as Cooperman (2007) observes, “to the typical instructional design convention of providing an introduction; presenting the students with a set of objectives; presenting new information; offering self-checked and graded quizzes, assignments, and exercises and then summarizing the key points of the lesson”.

So, when it should be about creating a culture of learning and practice in the classroom, it should be emulated in the e-classroom as well. A holistic bent to bringing this about will be to emphasize these aspects from all the subject areas that are being dealt with at a particular point in time and then to build instructions to focus on developing this tendency of a ‘setting’ culture. For example, the certificate programme in Bharatanatyam is of six months duration, out of which four months is the actual time the students receive for the classes and the rest of the two months spent in admission and exams, which can be divided into a 16-week plan. For a programme with six courses, offering the student plans on per week per course basis would total up a not-so-favourable number of instructional plan pages. So that this exercise is junked out, an option would be to create a setting keeping in view the new constructivist approach where the objectives, the outcomes of learning and the plan may emphasize the situatedness by building the field with an integrated plan wherein elements from different subjects are placed and approached to provide a holistic interconnectedness, a sense of an effective community of practice in the e-classroom setting. Gagne’s nine events of instruction can be adapted as has been shown here and developed into a lesson plan that would be a close-knit model encompassing weekly material of study within an instructional material design that derives from across different courses.

The lesson plan was chosen as a linking ground of instructional design where audio-visual sources, assessments, discussions and instructions could converge and through which the routine of f2f had to be translated into an online reality. The art of Bharatanatyam itself is a confluence of elements of music, rhythm, and dance and this meant that teaching skill courses had to ensure the presence of all these three, which was present in three different practical courses in the case of this programme, along with the theory ones in a synergized and progressive manner. Lesson planning, usually a step-by-step instruction guide and a blueprint for conducting a class or teaching a concept, could be transformed into a dynamic e-template or linking ground plan in the instructional design for course delivery. The interface, the Google classroom (available with *G suite/ Google Workspace*), is an easily available platform that has components that include *stream, classwork, people* and *grades* which easily fits the four-quadrant approach recommended for the online courses by the University Grants Commission. Moreover, like any LMS, text material, audio videos, discussion forums, and assessments can be uploaded to the classroom and accessed with ease by both the teacher and student on a single platform. The entire programme with six courses was adapted and designed to be offered, keeping in mind the principles of online learning associated with it.

The Vygotskian approach that has stressed social interaction in the development of cognition and its enunciation through the ‘zone of proximal development’ forms an important part of kinesthetic learning too (Vygotsky, 1978). This is emphasized in distance learning in dance largely in a blended learning format where interaction with the teacher and peers happen during f2f sessions. The same, when transferred to an online system, has to imbibe and ensure that *scaffolding* is provided for ZPD in a digitally built environment. Scaffolding, which consists of the activities provided by the educator to support the student as he or she is led through the ZPD has been designed to be part of the virtual learning environment in the e-lesson plan. The design is explained through its presence in three interrelated dimensions of Garrison’s (2003) Community of inquiry namely social presence, cognitive presence and teaching presence (Garrison & Cleveland, 2005). Social presence allows students to network with other students and teachers to foster positive relationships for topics of discussion and to better connect with the learning environment itself (Sutton & Basiel, 2013). Cognitive presence is where meanings are constructed and confirmed through reflection and discourse (Garrison, Anderson & Archer, 2001) and teaching presence consists of three components; design, facilitation of discourse and direct instruction. As Cutcher & Cook (2016) point out, the construction of communities of inquiry and in the case of the Arts, a community of practice is essential to the success of these approaches.

Results

The working structure of an e-Lesson plan

With many different digital templates for lesson plans being available online, it is totally upon the teacher to create the best model to make the lesson plans a composite linking ground for the different courses. Here, Gagne's nine *instructional events* and a readily available Google template were adapted to make a weekly lesson plan. The steps of the nine events include 1. Gain learner's attention, 2. Inform learner of objectives, 3. Stimulate recall of prior learning, 4. Present instruction, 5. Guided practice, 6. Independent performance, 7. Provide feedback, 8. Assess performance, 9. Enhance retention and transfer. The steps of the *events* are built into and designed as three main parts namely summary, implementation and assessment with sub-topics in the following order.

Figure 1: A collage showing some of the components of the weekly *e-Lesson Plan* of the Certificate programme in Bharatanatyam

I. Summary:

1. Subjects
2. Topic of study
3. Objective
4. Time allotment

II. Implementation:

1. Learning context
2. Procedure
 - a) Instructional material
 - b) Mode of practice
 - c) Practice checklist
 - d) Independent practice
 - e) Reflect and tell

III. Assessment

The weekly lesson plan forms the main resource given every week and was placed amongst a slew of other topics in the LMS (Figure 1). The contents consisted of a welcome message to learners in the form of a programme introductory video, a programme document that gave general information, programme learning outcomes, video tutorials on using the LMS, the procedure to submit assignments, self-learning material resources, graded formative practical assignments (1-16), graded theory assignments (3), a doubt box, schedule of virtual sessions, information about term-end exams along with supplementary viewing material for practicals and theory.

Summary

This contains the summary of subjects and topics that will be covered that week. It gives specific information on the course title/s and the contents for which resources and instructions are provided. Along with this, the objectives/learning outcomes for the week are stated. Specifying the time allotment according to the topics covered, especially for practical dance with definite instruction on duration, will help the distance learner to gauge the requisite duration of practice that one needs to put in each day. Below (Table 1) is the sample from the Week-3 e-lesson plan of the certificate programme.

Table 1: Summary

Summary

1. Subject(s): Course codes ODNL-11, ODNL-12, ODNL-13, ODN-01
2. Topic or Unit of Study:
Practical- Thattadavus 5 to 7, Asamyuta hastas, Introduction to tala
Theory: ODN-1 Unit-2, 3, 4
3. Objectives: At the end of this week, you shall be able to
 - Demonstrate thattadavus 5-7 in three speeds
 - Perform 1 & 2 nattadavus
 - Demonstrate the angas of tala along with their kriyas
 - Explain panchajaathi and derivation of 35 talas
 - Execute the talas with sollus for 7 thattadavus in first speed

- Render the sloka along with a demonstration of asamyutha hasta
- Explain the features and significance of Bharatanatyam, Mohiniattom and Kathakali

4. Time Allotment: 1/2 hour warm up, 2-hour practice and study every day.

Implementation

The **learning context** sets the ambience for the learning process. It provides the rationale and relevance of the concepts that would be taught and also is intended to recall prior learning (Table 2&3: Weeks 1 & 5). The instructions have to be conversational in nature with relevant titbits to arouse the interest of the learner. The learner is given general information on the progress of the week's activities. A distant learner is supposed to be self-motivated, but in the case of a physically demanding art form like dance, motivation to follow a practice routine is very important and this needs constant reminders from the teacher. This section provides scope for the establishment of caring and attentive relationships between the teacher and the distant learner.

Table 2: The learning context

Learning Context

This week's module introduces you to some basic concepts in Bharatanatyam. Before starting to learn any physical skill, warm-up exercises are done to gently tone the muscles involved in the performance. We shall be doing toning, balancing, strengthening, stamina building, posture correctional and breath-related exercises.....

The theory unit on Indian classical dance shall help you get some fundamental ideas on the topic.

Please remember to complete the assessment towards the end of the week. Happy dancing!

Table 3: The learning context

Learning Context

As you progressed through the nattadavus of 3, 5, 6 and 7 you would have noticed that you have used almost all the basic feet positions learnt in week 1. Nattadavus, as the name says, deals with positioning your feet hitherto not done before in thattadavu and the successive adavus take this aspect ahead with not just positioning them but creating elaborate patterns with both hands and feet..... The adi and rupaka talam in their three speeds help maintain rhythm and this week we shall be doing these along with an illustration of the various gati used in performance.

The **Procedure** gives a clear picture of how the objectives are materially substantiated with the provision of rich instructional resources, guided practice support, a practical checklist, demonstration and performance, self and collective reflection and finally assessment and feedback.

The *instructional material* contains the topics of the week in the form of audio, video and text. In the case of the three practical courses which were divided based on their main components- *Nritta* (pure technique), *Nritya* (expressional dance) and *Talas* (rhythm), a collaborative view was taken to include parts of each in every week's lesson plan. The courses may be dealt with separately too one after the other if the curriculum is designed to progress so. Each aspect of learning in Bharatanatyam skills involves practical demonstrations in music, tala, and the dance itself along with the text of these components. Designing a week's instructional material into three or four videos covering all the aspects mentioned above would be one way of doing it. But after considering pertinent issues that may arise like the footage of recording to be edited, the time taken to upload each video, accessibility by students, identification according to specific names and reusability for practice, it was chosen to make smaller videos, audio coupled with their texts as instructional material. The resources were linked from the videos made and uploaded to YouTube or google drive. The instructional material links of the Week 3 lesson plan are given in table 4.

Table 4: Instructional materials

Instructional material Video of

- Thattadavu 5
- Thattadavu 6
- Thattadavu 7
- Nattadavu 1 & 2
- Things to remember when doing Nattadavu
- Asamyuta hasta sloka
- Kriya of tala anga, jaathis
- Adi & rupaka tala
- Panchajaathi and 35 talas
- Tala for 1, 2 & 4th thattadavu
- Tala for 3rd thattadavu
- Tala for 3rd thattadavu
- Tala for third thattdavu 1,2 & 3 speeds
- Tala for 5th thattadavu
- Tala for 6th & 7th thattadavu

Audio of

- 5th thattadavu
- 6th thattadavu
- 7th thattadavu

Text of

- Asamyuta hasta sloka
 - Introduction to tala
 - Sollus of thattadavu and nattadavu
-

Mode of practice is a section that provides support and acts as a scaffold for the student. It instructs the student on how to progress and use the resources. It addresses the increased requirements for the personal guidance of the trainee. (Table 5: Week6)

A *practice checklist* encourages self-analysis and scope for correction in doing what has been learnt. It gives a green signal for the student to proceed to rehearse/ practice what has been learnt. This section points out the usual mistakes often made by learners and helps them countercheck their progress (Table 6: Week 1). A common folder called a *doubt box* can be of purpose here as an addition to the discussion forum that accompanies each topic as the student can deposit doubts in audio or video format too. The *doubt box* can be part of the *Assessment* in the classroom where submissions need not be made time-bound.

Table 5: The mode of practice

Mode of Practice

The previous advice of practising feet movements first before attempting arm movement/ simultaneous action with hands stands good in this case too. Certain nuances bring subtleness to the dance and some such ones are the gentle shoulder pull and push, attami- neck moves and drishti/glances. Practice these in front of a mirror and use them in the adavus on appropriate occasions as shown in the videos. As you may be quite clear by now regarding the hastas and abhinaya of dhyana shloka, practising the eye exercises taught this week shall help you further in bringing focus and sharpness to your glances while using hastas and facial abhinaya.

Table 6: The practice check-list

Practice check-list

Please follow the instructions in the video when performing adavus and refer to the instruction on basic posture check on your posture when practising. Stop and correct it in case you are doing it wrong. Use the help of a mirror to look at your positions. In the initial stages, a mirror helps to remove inaccuracies which are otherwise not perceived by oneself when performing.

Ask yourself if

- the knees are turned out enough in an aramandi,
 - you are raising the feet to touch the back and then placing when doing the first speed of the adavu,
 - you are erroneously pointing your toes when you take it back,
 - you are wrongly stamping hard with your heels or evenly placing the feet on the ground while tapping
 - the hands at your back are positioned well at the two sides of your hips
 - your thumb is not wrongly pointing outward and is placed in line with the other fingers
-

Independent practice provides guidelines and supportive resources necessary for repeated practice. Audio recordings which can be looped to repeat themselves when played help as a ready source for independent practice. This section can also be used to create awareness of health, nutrition and injury prevention

Reflect and tell! gets the students thinking about the areas dealt with through self-reflective questions. It lets the student form an evaluative summary of the entire week's activities. As Leijan. et al., point out, "Reflection stimulates students' awareness of their body and movement experiences, which is necessary for developing high-quality dance skills. ... reflection is essential for students to learn how the audience may perceive their performance or choreographic work" (2012). Though this programme gives fundamental training in technical skills with some creative choreography involved, a guided self-reflection gives space for the student to gain an analytical outlook, evaluate oneself, enhance retention and activate towards improvising and exploring the concepts learnt. This section can include a few guided tasks which can stimulate interest in the students for working out solo themes which may be later discussed in the live classes. Tasks for self-reflection will act as a motivation to shed initial hesitancy to take up collective reflection among their peer group to coordinate and innovate group choreography in real time.

Assessment

Assessments are in the form of audio-video recordings that can be uploaded to a shared file. Relevant weekly assessments will quantify the targets achieved and can be considered to determine definitive paths towards completion of the course. In distance learning courses where dropout cases are more than in regular courses, graded weekly assessments, motivate the students to perform well. The weekly grades will also help overcome problems of complacency and help build a spirit of healthy competition among peers. The additional option of resubmission of assessment gives scope for corrections following the feedback of the teacher. Though grades are presented elsewhere in the LMS, the questions and the links to access submissions of co-students can be provided within the lesson plan itself.

Outcomes of programme evaluation

Out of the many parameters for which data was collected using the survey method, the following table shows their perceptions of content, course delivery and its accessibility through google classroom, the effectiveness of the e-lesson plan as a composite tool and the responsiveness of the teacher.

As can be seen from the above (Figure 2), the perceptions of students pertaining to the content provided in the lesson plan were largely positive. All the twenty-one students gave a positive response to the question: if learning objectives were clear and the course content was organized and well planned. All the students

agreed that the short videos presented in the lesson plan enabled the students to learn practical techniques in a more focused and efficient manner.

Figure 2: Perceptions on content and workload

Though the survey was conducted online on google forms in Google Classroom, questions on the attributes of the teacher concerning skill and responsiveness were put as the very first question to maintain transparency and genuineness of the process (Figure 3). On various counts like teaching capability, presentation

Figure 3: Instructor skill and responsiveness

skills, promptness in grading and feedback the students felt that the teacher was effective. In terms of availability and providing motivation too, the teacher contributed well.

Apart from the content, the mode of delivery and accessibility of the course on the new platform was also received well (Figure 4). Twenty (95%) out of twenty-one students opined that the lesson plans with links to multimedia instructional material made it accessible at a single location. And almost all of them agreed that the google platform brought learning, assessment and interaction to the same platform. Half the students (11) strongly agreed along with almost the other half (9) to the weekly frequency of the lesson plan. It was felt that the availability of a weekly lesson plan with its weekly assessments made learning organized. Apart from this, the weekly assessments that were also inbuilt with the lesson plan itself were found to have helped in improved learning among the majority of students.

Figure 4: Design perceptions

The linking of Gmail accounts of registered students enabled easy accessibility of google classroom for the students and the availability of G-suite for the counsellor enabled larger cloud space in terms of auto-storage for the student's weekly video uploads (assessments). Finally, all (21) of them agreed that flexibility to learn dance at one's convenient place and time, the very motto of ODL learning was truly effected by teaching-learning of the programme on the web. The outcome of such a venture showed positive results as the enrollment figure tripled to forty-eight in the successive session of July 2020.

Conclusion

In an open and distance education programme where the proximity of f2f has been replaced by online teaching, the paper has shown how an interface like an e-lesson plan can be designed to become a dynamic linking ground and a composite tool for teaching traditional dance skills. It has shown how the e-lesson plan model has helped in streamlining information and activities thereby bringing consistency and standardization in instruction delivery in an online classroom setting. With an effective presence of elements required of a community of practice, the integrated e-lesson plan thus designed, can help scaffold the learner with directions and possibilities to gain cognitive and skill development in a seamlessly easy manner. A programme evaluation conducted also confirmed the effectiveness of the e-lesson plan in the online teaching-learning of the dance form. The majority of the enrolled students agreed with the online delivery of instructional design with lesson plans as the focal point of resource.

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² Universities that offer such courses include Indirakala sangeet Vishwavidyalaya, Khairagarh; KalaiKaviri, Trichy; Sastra University, Tanjore and IGNOU, New Delhi, among the few.